

Building ProSPA Hardware as part of ESA's PROSPECT Package- Current Status and Updates.

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Introduction: The Package for Resource Observation and in-Situ Prospecting for Exploration, Commercial exploitation and Transportation (PROSPECT) is being developed by the European Space Agency (ESA) to support international lunar surface exploration missions. It comprises a drilling element (ProSEED – PROSPECT Sample Excavation and Extraction Drill, developed by Leonardo S.p.A., Italy) and a Sample Processing and Analysis element – ProSPA (being developed by The Open University, UK). PROSPECT is designed to investigate volatiles and other resources from the perspectives of both science (e.g. nature, abundance, distribution and processing of lunar volatiles) and of exploration (e.g. availability and extractability of materials for In-Situ Resource Utilization – ISRU).

Instrument implementation: The first flight of the PROSPECT package will be an ESA contribution to NASA's CLPS programme, and is intended to visit the southern hemisphere of the Moon in the second half of this decade.

The functions of ProSPA are distributed across two physical units – (1) a Solids Inlet System (SIS) comprising a series of single-use sample ovens on a rotary carousel together with a sample imager, and (2) a miniature (37 x 27 x 13 cm) chemical analysis laboratory incorporating two mass spectrometers and associated sample and reference gas processing and control systems.

The combined mass of both ProSPA hardware elements is 13 kg.

ProSPA System Diagram, showing the SIS (bordered by blue lines, bottom left), and the AL (bordered by green lines) components.

ProSPA Development Status:

Solids Inlet System (SIS): The engineering model of the SIS (EM SIS) is now well advanced, with carousel, working and dummy ovens, tapping station and SamCam all mounted onto the baseplate, with 3D-printed aluminium covers that will act as a frame for MLI in the final flight model.

All of the individual components that form the SIS have undergone their own development and testing campaigns, some of which are outlined in greater detail in other abstracts at this meeting, as well as being described in greater detail in various publications [1,2]. Functional testing of the EM SIS under construction has been carried out within the Open University spaceflight cleanroom suite using the RAL-developed ProSPA EM LES (Local Electronics System).

Now that the EM SIS has been built, it is ready to undergo thermal vacuum and vibration testing as a complete subassembly, before moving on to building a Proto-Flight Model (PFM SIS) for acceptance and qualification testing and ultimately usage on the lunar surface.

After the PFM SIS has been built, a Ground Reference Model of the SIS (GRM SIS) will be produced to support pre-mission Science Team activities, as well as being a fully working reference model on Earth for use during the lunar surface operations of the PFM SIS.

Assembled EM SIS, with carousel, EM and mass dummy ovens, SamCam, tapping station, and alignment collet all mounted onto the baseplate.

Assembled EM SIS undergoing testing with EM LES in OU spaceflight cleanroom.

Analytical Laboratory (AL): ProSPA AL development has followed a slightly different pathway to that of the SIS, with some of the functions of an EM being carried out using the ProSPA Bench Development Model (BDM), as well as other smaller test rigs for different aspects of the AL, such as valve function/leak testing, gas separation and cleanup using cold fingers, getters, and reactors, and magnetic sector mass spectrometer (MSS) geometry and functionality testing (e.g. [3]).

Within the ProSPA AL is also an ion trap mass spectrometer (ITMS), which has undergone its own separate, accelerated development, firstly to form a standalone instrument (Exospheric Mass Spectrometer (EMS), as ESA's contribution to PITMS for NASA CLPS, led by NASA Goddard [4,5]), and following that mission, further iterations and improvements.

*Left: PITMS EMS
GRM ITMS Sensor*

*Right: ProSPA GRM ITMS
sensor in development.*

With all of these different elements of the AL having been developed and tested in different ways, the first AL model to be built will be the GRM, for which the GRM ITMS already exists. Parts for the GRM MSS have been procured and the build for this mass spectrometer is expected to commence summer 2025. Long lead-time components, such as heaters and two-way valves, having been tested using the BDM and other test rigs, have also started to be delivered to the Open University, in readiness for link-

ing up both GRM mass spectrometers to form a complete GRM AL iteration later in 2025.

The GRM AL will be used for environmental testing, such as thermal vacuum and vibration testing, and like the eventual GRM SIS, will be available to support pre-mission Science Team activities, as well as in-mission support/testing during lunar surface operations.

Following the GRM AL build and testing phase, the PFM AL will be built. Like the PFM SIS, this will undergo acceptance and qualification testing before being launched as part of the ProSPA flight hardware.

References:

- [1] Mortimer, J. et al. (2018) Planetary and Space Science, **158**, 25-33.
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- [3] Verchovsky, A. B. et al. (2020) Planetary and Space Science, **181**, 104830.
- [4] Cohen, B. A. et al. (2024), The Planetary Science Journal, **5**:212.
- [5] Cohen, B. A. et al. (2025) The Planetary Science Journal, **6**:14.